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Research Article

COUNSELLING IN THE MANAGEMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETIC MELLITUS

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Abstract:

Objective: To evaluate counselling to improve consistence in administration of T2 Diabetic Mellitus patients.

Study Design: Cross sectional investigation.

Place and Duration of Study: This investigation was led at the Department of Medicine, Al Nafees Medical college, Hospital Islamabad from January 2018 to September 2018.

Materials and Methods: Sample size was 61 cases, educated assent was acquired from all patients enlisted, proforma was planned and filled for every patient. Data was analyzed on SPSS adaptation 21, Chi – square test was applied for statistical centrality.

Results: In our examination sexual orientation circulation of patients in the investigation populace, guys 27 (44.24%) and females 34 (55.71%), the commonest age bunch 50 – 59 years, guys 12 (19.67), females 20 (32.78%), rustic 44(72.12%) metropolitan 17 (27.86%). Out of 61 patients 5 lost development, one demise because of lethal entanglement of DM and 55 were followed up. Out of 55patients40 (72.72%) improved consistence subsequent to directing male 21 (38.18%) and female 19 (34.54%) separately, mean of HbA1c was 8.1 +.2. Out of 55 patients 15 (27.27%) didn't improve in consistence in the wake of guiding, male 5 (9.09%) and female 10 (18.18%), mean of HbA1c was 11.4 + .3. Chi – square worth was huge (p-esteem <0.05)

Conclusion: There is huge improvement in consistence level subsequent to directing in T2DM patients. Medical services suppliers, drug specialists and different experts should assume their part to improve the patient's information on sickness and therapy of T2DM.

Key Words: Counseling, improvement, T2 Diabetic Mellitus

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INTRODUCTION:

Type 2 Diabetic Mellitus (T2DM) is the most prevalent type of Diabetic Mellitus, which is 90% - 95% of all diabetic patients [1] and is relied upon to increment 439 million by 2030 [2,3]. It is a worldwide general medical condition and keeps a consistent expansion in created areas, for example, US and Japan. Also, it has become significant issue at pestilence rate in agricultural nations, for example, India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Brazil and Indonesia [4]. Among which the rates are 12.1%, 16.98% and 9.7% in India, Pakistan and China respectively [5,6,7]. Increasing pace of youth corpulence overall is not kidding hazard factor for T2DM. [8]

There are many factors prompting non – consistence in the administration of T2DM. [9] Adherence to way of life changes (diet and exercise) and medication treatment improves compliance¹⁰.

Medications and way of life alteration to control T2DM and related conditions must be viable through consistence to the doctor counsel. World Health Organization (WHO) has demonstrated that adherence to long haul treatment for persistent diseases in created nations midpoints around 50%¹¹. Consistence rates are diminished for patients with ongoing sicknesses than with intense infections, so decrease in adherence is generally fast following a half year of therapy¹². Such decreased adherence brings about chronic weakness results as well as significantly affects medical services costs.¹¹

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Total 61 patients of T2 Diabetic Mellitus were enlisted from outpatient centers of medication division of Isra University Hospital, Islamabad after educated assent was acquired. Study configuration was cross-sectional interventional and dependent on non – likelihood purposive examining. Study period was from January 2018 to September 2018. Consistence was characterized as adherence to doctor's recommendation with respect to count

calories, work out, drug treatment and improvement in HbA1c level. These patients were directed and followed up month to month for a very long time to notice the improvement in consistence subsequent to advising. Data was analyzed on SPSS v.21, Chi – square test was applied for statistical significance.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Age over 30 years
2. Willing to participate

Prohibition Criteria:

1. Age under 30 years
2. unwilling

RESULTS:

Table 1. shows distribution of patients in the study population, males 27 (44.24%) and females 34 (55.71%), the age group 50 – 59 years, males 12 (19.67%), females 20 (32.78%),

Table 2. shows distribution of patients according to residential area, rural 44 (72.12%) male 23 (37.70%), female 21 (34.42%. Urban 17 (27.86%), male 4(6.55%), female 13 (21.31%).

Table 3. shows distribution of patients according to outcome of follow-up. Out of 61 patients 5 lost follow up, one death due to fatal complication of DM and 52 were followed up.

Table 4. shows distribution of patients according to improvement in compliance after counselling in the management of T2DM, out of 55 patients 40 (72.72% improved, male 21 (38.18%), female 19 (34.54%), mean of HbA1c was 8.1 ±.2

Table 5. shows distribution of patients according to non- improvement in compliance after counselling in the management of T2DM. Out of 55 patients 15 (27.27%) did not improve, male 5 (9.09%), female 10 (18.18%), mean of HbA1c was 11.4 ± .3.

Table No.1: Distribution of patients according to age and gender(n=61)

Age groups	Male		Female	
	No.	%	No.	%
30 – 39 years	7	11.47	1	1.64
40 – 49 years	6	9.83	8	13.11
50 – 59 years	12	19.67	20	32.79
> 60 years	2	3.27	5	8.19
Total	27	44.24	34	55.73

Table No. 2: Distribution of patients according to residential area (n=61)

Residence	Male		Female	
	No.	%	No.	%
Rural	23	37.70	21	34.42
Urban	4	6.55	13	21.31
Total	27	44.25	34	55.73

Table No. 3: Distribution of patients according to outcome follow up n=61

Group	Number
Follow up	55
Lost follow up	5*
Death	1*

*All were females

Table No. 4: Patient improvement in compliance after counselling(n=55)

Gender	Number	%age	Mean of HbA1c % + SD
Males improved	21	38.18	8.1±.2
Females improved	19	34.54	
Total	40	72.72	

*p – value <0.05

Table No.5: Patient non - improvement in compliance after counselling (n=55)

Gender	Number	%age	Mean of HbA1c % +SD
Males not improved	5	9.09	11.4± .3
Females not improved	10	18.18	
Total	15	27.27	

*p – value <0.05

DISCUSSION:

Non-adherence is a major factor that could lead to morbidity and mortality in diabetic patients. World Health Organization have emphasized that “increasing the effectiveness of adherence interventions may have a far greater impact on the health of the population than any improvement in specific medical treatments. Adherence to long-term therapy for chronic illnesses among developed countries averages only 50%. [11]

In our study population improvement in compliance rate after counselling is 72.72%. Which is comparable with study done by Olufunsho Awodele et al (Lagos, Nigeria 2015) [13] in which Overall improvement in compliance rate was 86.8 %. Likewise, other studies reported by Krishnaveni Kandasamy et al (Tamil Nadu, India 2017) [14], Ann

Marry Swaroop et al(Bangalore, India 2016) [15] Anoop Kumar et al (Kerala, India 2015) [16], Shareef J et al (Karnataka, India 2016) [17], Mathew EM et al (Tamil Nadu, India 2014) [18], Kumari G et al (New Delhi, India) [19] and Malik S. et all (Karachi Pakistan 2016)²⁰ have demonstrated significant improvement in glycemic control and other end points.

Our study is inconsistent with study conducted by Bhurji N et al (UK, Canada 2016) [21] on South Asian countries patients from Pakistan, India, Bangladesh living in Europe vs Western countries patients with type 2 diabetes. Overall, there was little improvement in HbA1c level although other outcomes did improve. The smaller studies in India demonstrated significant improvement in glycemic control and other end points. [21]

CONCLUSION:

It can be concluded that there is significant improvement in compliance level after counselling in T2DM patients. Health care professionals should play their role to improve the patient's knowledge of disease and treatment of T2DM.

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